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Network Anomalies Detection in Smart Grid System using Machine Learning

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1 Abstract

Detecting anomalies in a smart grid system has become critical due to the increase in cyberattacks. The fuzzy and dynamic nature of cyberattacks has caused a lot of challenges in detecting anomalies leading to abnormal predictions in a smart grid system. That has allowed cyber criminals to deploy various attacks on the network. Due to the rapidly expanding industry of cyber-physical systems, the traditional power grid has been upgraded into a communication infrastructure network. However, this upgrade has led to cyberattacks such as Ukraine power system cyberattack 2015, Iran aramco attack 2017 and New York smart grid system attack 2018 causing a lot damage to the systems, the economy and livelihoods. The aim of this dissertation is to explore anomaly detections in smart grid systems using machine learning models. Due to the integrated nature of the smart grid system, it has inherent vulnerabilities which attackers can exploit because of its integrated design. Such threat actors take advantage of these flaws, which has an enormous effect on embedded systems. This problem is rampant because of the potentially extensive size of these networks, which makes continuous monitoring by technicians or specialists impracticable. For this problem to be effectively resolved, automatic detection of entities that present anomalous activity is essential. Machine learning methods are important in transforming the security of smart grid systems from merely facilitating secure communication between devices to security-based intelligence systems. The dissertation proposes integrating multiple supervised machine learning-based models into a single Intrusion Detection Systems to complement each other and mitigate the shortcomings of the other models that will be suitable to detect anomalies in the smart grid communication network effectively.

Table of Contents

1	Abstract.....	1
2	Introduction	4
3	BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK	7
3.1	Cyber-Physical Systems	8
3.2	Anomaly detection.....	11
3.3	Smart grid Attacks	15
3.4	Machine Learning for Network Anomaly Detection.....	19
4	Methodology	22
4.1	Model development.....	22
4.2	Data.....	22
4.3	Modelling.....	25
4.4	Model Architecture	26
4.5	Model Performance Metrics.....	33
5	Evaluation	35
5.1	Binary Classification Model.....	35
5.2	Three Class classification Model	38
6	Future Work.....	41
7	Conclusion.....	42
	REFERENCE.....	44

2 Introduction

The traditional power grid has been converted from analogue to embedded computer-based control, often communicating through computer-based networks. The power grid has now been made vulnerable to cyber-attacks due to the automation of its functionalities for interacting with the physical world [1].

Before understanding what, a smart grid is, one must first understand what 'smart' means. According to the European Electricity Network, Smart is "an electricity network that can effectively combine the operations of all users linked to it, including generators, consumers, and those that perform both, in order to efficiently offer sustainable, economic, and secure electrical supplies. It also employs innovative products and services with intelligent monitoring, control, communication, and self-healing technologies to better facilitate connection and operation, provides information, enhances supply reliability and security, and includes societal requirements and governmental requirements edicts" [2].

In essence, the smart grid is a modernization of the current electrical system that improves the ability of customers and utilities to monitor, control, and predict energy use [3]. It is created by integrating advanced embedded sensors, communications technologies, information systems, computerization, and control system with the physical power grid. [4]. The fundamental components of the power grid are generation, transmission, distribution, and consumption. This grid was introduced at the beginning of the 21st century. Upon its conception, it sought to include bidirectional communication infrastructure in conventional (traditional power) grids to enable information and communication technologies (ICTs) at any component of power grids [5-7]. As a collection of digital systems, it is gradually replacing the antiquated infrastructure that delivers power to our homes and businesses.

A smart grid is a network of generating, transmission, and distribution components that transmit power from power plants and distributed generation to diverse loads. These elements are managed by sophisticated devices that must be safeguarded. [7]. Also, the smart grid interacts with electrical and communication levels using several communication architectures, including area networks, power system architectures of generation, transmission, and distribution, and ICT architecture providing integrity

features to the existing systems. Power plants are used in bulk generation. Plant controllers communicate with other domains via wide-area networks (WANs) and substations via local area networks (LANs) (LANs). Substation devices, electric storage systems, field devices, and data collectors are all part of the transmission level. In the distribution domain, data collectors communicate with WANs, substation LANs, and field area networks (FANs). Field gadgets, on the other hand the Communication Systems of Smart Grids [5].

The existing power system's limitations and degradation are important reasons for developing the smart power grid [5], [6]. Since its inception and widespread use, the traditional electrical infrastructure has deteriorated. This has resulted in flaws that distort power quality and dependability and render it incompatible with modern load demands. Voltage instability, intermittency, curtailments, blackouts, and imbalanced or heavy load circumstances all contribute to such inadequacies. To address these shortcomings, remote monitoring and control technologies have been upgraded and integrated into conventional grids. As a result, the smart grid, which consists of hybrid networks comprised of electrical grids and a supporting information and communication technology (ICT) network, was introduced. Smart grids rely on a variety of ICT-based services to carry out their functions. The Internet of Things (IoT) is one of the most popular [5]. According to Gartner, Inc., there will be around 20.8 billion connected items in use globally by 2020 [8]. Smart grids will transform the electricity business, making it more sustainable and flexible to modern power demands [6]. The smart grid will benefit us in a variety of ways. To begin, the grid will allow consumers to actively participate in the electrical market. Secondly, through this grid, all types of electrical generation and storage systems will be integrated using simplified interconnection processes and universal interoperability standards. Lastly, the grid will operate resiliently against attacks and natural disasters [9]. Most importantly, the Smart Grid is anticipated to significantly improve distributed intelligence and demand response, due to the integration of advanced processing and communication technology [10].

Despite the various benefits of the smart grid, there are some associated risks. Millions of devices and infrastructures are connected and interconnected utilising communication links in the smart grid environment, exposing the grid and customers to potential security

risks [3]. In the United Kingdom, for example, energy worth £400 million is stolen each year, resulting in inflated customer bills [11]. Another example is the prevalence of smart grid attacks, such as the 2015 Ukraine power grid cyber-attack, which resulted in a three-hour blackout and affected 225,000 customers [12]. In 2019, a similar attempt hit a major electrical company in Johannesburg, South Africa, causing serious disruptions in power supply [13]. Many aspects of cyber-security, such as security availability, integrity, confidentiality, and accountability, increase the risk of compromising the smart grid [7]. This is a result of the highly distributed properties of the modern grid. Aside from the financial gain for a malicious actor, a cyber-attack can also critically affect the grid processes and directly impact its overall resilience and safety [14]. Now, cyber-attacks can be observed at various generation, transmission, distribution, and consumer levels. There are several Cyber-Physical attack techniques, such as, distributed denial-of-service attacks, usage loggers, smart meter rootkits, meter-based viruses [3], man in the middle and false data injection [10]. There are also, threats that arise naturally due to weather, fire, or animal activity; human error; and equipment failure [7]. Anomalies refer to patterns in data that do not conform to a well-defined characteristic of normal patterns. They are generated by various abnormal activities on the smart grid network [15]. Malicious threats in the smart grid communication networks are a major cause of attacks in the smart grid [10]. To improve the grid's resilience against such attacks, utility companies are investing about 23 billion dollars in smart grid infrastructure. Although infrastructure changes will go a long way to help curb this menace, that alone will not prevent cyber-attacks on the grid. To address this issue, advanced ML and AI techniques can be leveraged by the utilities. These techniques can learn user behaviour from historical data and easily identify anomalies in user behaviour [7]. Machine learning can use smart grid data to understand the underlying structure, gain useful insights, detect anomalies, and generate hypotheses. It can detect theft and understand user consumption behaviour at a particular feeder. The role of Predictions in power systems is significant as they are typically used to plan future aggregated electricity demand, future system supply, estimate flexibility and reserve services requirements, or operational management of distribution networks [7].

The three levels categorized into energy generation, Transmission, Distribution, and end-user infrastructures have different probabilities for the deployment of theft and different vulnerabilities exploited by malicious actors. Such factors are not considered

when a method is designed to detect anomalies on the smart grid network [14]. Existing anomaly detection techniques mostly monitor a single system or network by conducting local analysis for attacks. Hence, no communication and interaction exist between instances of such a standalone anomaly detection technique [15].

However, utilizing a hybrid data-driven machine learning model has proven more robust than adopting a single model in detecting attack vectors underpinning smart power grid attacks. Such hybrid methods are considered combinatorial use of two or more data-driven models. In such methods, the entire theft detection method leverages the analytic process of each candidate model to achieve a specific action. All achieved actions are subsequently integrated into one detection system to complement each other and mitigate the limitations of the others [14].

Hence, for the security of large networks and large IT ecosystems like the smart grid network, a hybrid data-driven model will be extremely efficient for an intrusion detection system to detect sophisticated and highly distributed attacks [14], [15].

The contributions of the dissertation are as follows:

1. Firstly, this project introduces a hybrid and aggregation of data-driven Machine Learning models to efficiently and successfully detect abnormalities on the smart grid network than a single machine learning model.
2. Lastly, to prove the efficiency of other machine learning models by comparing their efficiency to the efficiency of the Support Vector Machine.

3 BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

This section provides an overview of the project's incentives, background, and review of comparable work. Firstly, the context of cyber-physical systems and their relevance in traditional physical systems, such as smart grid systems for power generation, transmission, and distribution, is described. Next, the security threats and challenges of smart grid systems are reviewed, including malignant anomalies, malicious cyber-attacks, and physical attacks. This is followed by a review of different kinds of Cyber-Physical Systems attacks, including the causes and mode of attacks, the impact of attacks, including a case study cited as an example – the Ukraine Power grid cyber-attack. In addition, a review of smart grid systems attacks and their impacts is presented. This is

followed by a discussion on anomaly detection, types of anomalies, and its techniques, in identifying network anomalies on smart grid systems. The anomaly detection work includes an overview of the various machine learning techniques used by researchers to find anomalies in smart grid systems, as well as information on the shortcomings of each approach and how to improve it.

3.1 Cyber-Physical Systems

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) is a term that defines an orchestration of physical components and computational processes, where 'cyber' and 'physical' parts are coupled together in feedback loops, continuously affecting each other, Ilge Akkaya [16]. Cyber physical Systems include, smart grid, autonomous automobile systems, medical monitoring, industrial control systems, robotics systems, and automatic pilot avionics

These systems combine the integrations of cyber systems (computational systems and communication networks) with physical processes (electromechanical, structural, chemical, and biological systems). CPS is an important system in technological advancement because they transform how humans interact with engineered systems. CPS is composed of many heterogeneous components, which requires data-driven and complex models to capture its complexities and to define the sub-systems and their behaviour. The systems are encouraged to display three fundamental qualities: security, safety, and sustainability when utilised to build critical infrastructures. Many research studies have been emerging to realise these systems with the attributes mentioned. There are various kinds of Cyber-Physical Systems, and includes Information Technology, Gas Fuel manufacturing, Blockchain, Artificial Intelligence, Smart Manufacturing, Cloud Computing, the Internet of Things (IoT), and Smart Grids. However, regardless of the advantages and improvements made in CPS, one of the consistent challenges and concerns faced is the security aspect, which makes them vulnerable to different attacks posed on the control elements, network, and physical systems.

3.1.1 Smart grid Systems

A well-known application of CPS systems in the energy sector is Smart grid systems. Smart grid systems (SG) are innovations that provide solutions to the limitations of traditional grid systems like vulnerabilities, operational constraints, outages, and carbon emissions by providing reliable, efficient, secure, and quality energy in the power chain.

These innovations are manufactured and implemented using advanced digital and automated systems, intelligent tracking, modern monitoring, and communicative technologies to maximise the power system generation, distribution, and consumption quality.

The SG is made up of both physical power systems and cyber information systems. The integration of physical and cyber systems enables unprecedented levels of automation and human-machine interactions. The cyber environment's uncertainties and hostilities have raised new concerns for modern power systems. It is critical to have a system that maintains state awareness and an accepted level of operational normalcy in the face of disturbances, including unanticipated and hostile threats. C. G. Rieger *et al.*, D. Wei and K. Ji [17], [18].

Figure 2.1.1 Comprehensive substation automation architecture with various access configurations [1]

The systems that make up the SG architecture are power, communication, and information. Proper architecture is required to enable the smart grid to actualize its goals and operations. A fundamental understanding of the effects of power network topology and integrated network control with Big Data utilization are necessary for design of SG systems. Additionally, understanding the intricate interactions between the physical layer and the cyber layer—which also includes the supporting communication, information, and computational system is crucial. The SG architecture can be structured into six layers, the physical layer, control layer, data communication layer, network layer, supervisory layer, and management layer. The layers are shown in Figure 2.1. The first two layers, the physical layer, and the control layer can be jointly seen as the physical environment of the system. The data communication layer and network layer comprise the cyber environment of the power grid. The supervisory layer and management layer constitute the higher-level application layer where services and human-machine interactions take place.

Figure 2.1.2 shows the hierarchical architecture of smart grid systems

The network layer concerns the topology of the architecture. It comprises two major components: network formation and routing. Because SG is a network of networks, manifold potential vulnerabilities appear that allow privacy and security attacks on different layers of the architecture and the energy chain from generation, transmission, distribution, and consumption. Data flows between the SG systems configurations as it is digitalized and comprises a variety of nodes, sensors, and network and communication devices. Unfortunately, through the integration of these systems, many vulnerabilities arise such as cyber-attacks, and physical attacks, Y. Mo *et al.* [19]. These vulnerabilities are observed in the network with events and observations that deviate significantly from the majority of the data and do not conform to a well-defined behaviour.

The infrastructure and architecture of SG systems encountered numerous challenges and security threats. According to the security levels (A. Lee and T. Brewer, A.R. Metke and R.L. Ekl), [20], [21]; The security and challenges of these systems can be examined in terms of authentication, authorization, and privacy of the technologies; from a technical and non-technical perspective; according to the source of security threats; from a human and non-human perspective; according to the cause of threats; from a fault or breakdown of a unit as the generation, transmission, or distribution, and operational failure; from a natural or non-natural cause according to the factors responsible; or in terms of deliberate cause, for instance, organized crimes involving hacking, rioting, terrorism, cybercrimes, vandals, energy theft, sabotage, coercion, disruption of services, etc. indeliberate causes such as failure of equipment, commanding operation due to false data injection, information leakage to an external source (Khelifa and Abla, Sanjab *et al.*) [22], [23].

3.2 Anomaly detection

Anomaly detection is the identification of rare patterns, observations, and events in the data spectrum that raises suspicion due to their deviation from the normal characteristics and behaviour associated with the data. Anomalous data are connected to problems or rare events such as fraud detection, structural defects, malfunctioning equipment, cyber-attacks, etc. Identification of these abnormalities, causes, and their nature are necessary, and interesting aspects of data mining research for engineers and data analysts.

3.2.1 Types of Anomalies

The literature acknowledges numerous methods for differentiating between various anomaly kinds. Barnett and Lewis, Dixon, W.J, Schluter, C., and Trede, M., [24–26] distinguish between contaminants, which are observations from a different distribution, and extreme but genuine members of the main population, i.e., irregular fluctuations at the tails of the focal distribution.

Aggarwal et al. [27], [28] made a distinction between a *weak outlier* (noise) and a *strong outlier* (a significant deviation from normal behaviour). Fawzy, A., et al., Zhang, Y., [29], [30] sub-divided types of anomalies in events that take place in real-world scenarios, and measurement *errors*, such as a faulty wireless sensor. Overall classification is presented by Hair et al. [31] with the classes of anomalies, indicating the underlying reasons for their deviant nature: a *procedural error* (e.g., a coding mistake), an *extraordinary event* (such as a hurricane), *observation* (unexplained deviation), and a *unique value combination* (which has normal values for its attributes). King J. et al. [32] made a distinction between 9 different types of anomalies.

A broad classification is made by Chandola, V. et al., [33], which differentiates between three general categories. *Point anomaly* refers to one or several individual cases that are deviant from the rest of the data. In a practical example, if a person typically uses five litres of gasoline for their automobile every day but on any given day it uses fifty litres, it is a point anomaly. A *contextual or conditional anomaly* appears normal at first, but deviant when an explicitly selected context is taken into account, Song, X. et al. [34], For instance, credit card spending is typically higher around holidays like Christmas and New Year's than it is throughout the rest of the year. Finally, a *collective anomaly* refers to a collection of data points that belong together and, as a group, deviate from the rest of the data.

3.2.1.1 Network Anomaly Detection Techniques

In searching network data for anomalies that are relatively rare observations, the development and security teams will inevitably encounter different kinds of weak and strong outliers. This is because the line of distinction between different types of anomalies changes as malicious actors adopt different strategies while preparing their attacks. In addition, data patterns are based on complexity, seasonality, and time, thus

requiring sophisticated methods to identify actual changes to ascertain noises and outrageous events.

For all these reasons, the taxonomy of network anomaly techniques can be categorised into three: Data science, Machine Learning, and Deep Learning approach, Statistical learning and Information Theory

1. Data Science, Machine Learning, and Deep Learning approach.

These approaches are the recent approach to analysing and detecting the network anomalies in Cyber-Physical systems and Smart Grid systems. These techniques include Supervised, Unsupervised and Semi-Supervised Learning. The approach mostly used by researchers to detect network anomalies can be generally classified into two; Classification and Clustering techniques

Classification techniques are supervised learning anomaly detection techniques used when a complete set of labelled binary (normal and abnormal) or multi-class (attack, natural disaster, and working operation) datasets are provided over a period of time. These datasets are most times imbalanced i.e. the percentage of each dataset is not equal and varies significantly. This type of technique involves training a classifier. To apply a network anomaly detection classifier, a network expert provides details of the characteristics (features) of the detection system, and an attack with a known pattern can be detected as well as normal patterns. The technique is solely dependent on the attack's signature as a system, which is capable of detecting an attack only if its signature has been provided earlier by a network expert. The advantage lies in their capability to detect completely novel attacks, assuming that they exhibit ample deviations from the normal profile. The major algorithm used in classification techniques to approach network anomaly detection includes:

Support Vector Machine

Bayesian Network

Genetic Algorithm

Artificial Neural Network

Deep Neural Networks

Clustering techniques is an unsupervised learning anomaly detection technique applied when there is no pre-labelled data to extract rules for grouping the datasets (Jain et al. 1999) [35]. This approach is used based on the intrinsic properties of the data itself. The working assumption is that in most cases, the majority of the instances in the data are normal and therefore clustered within the same centroid, and the subsequent instances which do not fit well are then considered anomalies with different distant scores. There are two popular evaluation metrics for this approach; this includes the Silhouette coefficient and Dunn's Index. The major algorithm used in clustering techniques to approach network anomaly detection includes the following but not all:

K- Means clustering

Improved K-Means Clustering

Isolation Forest – Ensemble Algorithm

Density Based Clustering

K-Nearest Neighbour

Local Outlier Factor (LOF)

2. Statistical Learning.

The statistical learning approach is the traditional modelling approach to detect anomalies in the network. Intrusion detection approaches have also been created utilising statistical theories; for example, Ye and Chen (2001) [36] use the well-established chi-square theory for anomaly detection. A profile of routine events in an information system is built using this technique. The primary idea behind this method is to recognise both big deviations from normal as anomalous and intrusions. The Statistical Signal Processing approach is another option. This technique is based on detecting an abrupt shift in the network. Network abnormalities are defined in two ways by Thottan and Ji (2003) [37]: Anomalies corresponding to network failures and performance issues, as well as security-related issues such as DoS attacks. Another statistical method is Principal Component Analysis (PCA). PCAs are linear combinations of p random variables (A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p) which can be characterised as uncorrelated, with their variances sorted in order from high to low, or their total variance equal to the variance of the original data.

3. Information Theory:

An anomaly detection model can be built using information-theoretic measures. Several measures, like as entropy, conditional entropy, relative entropy, information gain, and information cost, are employed to explain the properties of the network dataset, according to Lee and Xiang (2001) [38]. To establish whether a model is suitable for evaluating the new dataset, information-theoretic measurements are used. Appropriate anomaly detection models can be created using the aforementioned approaches. To evaluate the performance of a model, supervised anomaly detection approaches require a training dataset followed by test data.

3.3 Smart grid Attacks

Any critical infrastructure is susceptible to attack. The majority of successful attacks on the smart grid combine multiple of the system's weak components. The mitigation and security approach used around and within it will define how big or minor the vulnerability is. Specific components and security standards are required for the smart grid to function. There are numerous approaches to classifying and describing vulnerabilities. On a device or entity level, or as a combination of those entities, we can analyze the smart grid's vulnerabilities. A list of devices that have specific vulnerabilities and important purposes on the grid is listed below in Table 3.1, (Schwars K. et al., Meliopoulos S. et al. 2011) [39], [40]:

Operational Systems	IT systems	Communication Protocols	Endpoints	Human Factors
Generators	PCs	Wi-Fi (IP)	Electric Vehicles	Human Training
Transformers	Servers	ZigBee	Smart Meters	Social Engineering
SCADA	Apps	4G	Mobile Devices	Phishing
PMU	DBs	DNP3	IEDs	Data Transfer

PLC	Web Services	IEC 60870		
Smart meters		IEC 61850		

Table 3.1: Vulnerable Grid Entities

3.3.1 The Physical attack

The SG footprint significantly increases due to the link between consumer home and business networks to other information networks that connect them with the control centers and sub-stations. This calls for the installation of equipment on consumer property that is likely to be a part of the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), which transfers power usage statistics and various other crucial pieces of information between customers and dedicated data aggregation sites or control centers. Furthermore, sophisticated and expensive technology such as sensors are installed in easily attacked public spaces, and these make them attractive targets for attacks because of their public availability. The utility will typically suffer negative consequences from the expenses associated with equipment replacement attacks and the service costs required by people performing system repairs or replacements.

Attacks on publicly accessible physical infrastructure can have a big impact on the SG as a whole. Blackouts and surge-related equipment damage can be caused by physical grid components that are managing or directing current being compromised.

3.3.2 Cyber Attacks

The various types of cyber-attacks on CPS and SG systems are discussed in this section (Dong et al., 2015, Humayed et al., 2017) [41], [42].

1. Network Attacks

An attempt to obtain unauthorized access to an organization's networks and data to perform malicious attacks is known as a network attack. The two primary categories of network assaults are: **passive** where attackers obtain access to a network to monitor or steal sensitive data without alteration, **and active** where attackers alter data, either by deleting, encrypting, or doing something else to it while gaining access to the network. The following attacks target a network due to bad network design, reckless users, or improper software or hardware configuration [43].

a. Denial of service:

A denial-of-service (DoS) is an attack that prevents a computer or other device from being used by its legitimate users by interfering with the device's normal computing operations. DoS attacks usually work by flooding a targeted machine with requests until normal traffic cannot be processed, which denies service to additional users e.g. apache, smurf, Neptune, ping of death, back, mail bomb, UDP storm, etc. One of the characteristics of a DoS assault is that it is launched from a single computer. Also, it is one of the dreadful attacks because there is no prior access to the targeted devices.

b. Probe

An actual attack to breach a host or network typically starts with a probing attack. These attacks do not specifically cause harm, but they are still seen as major risks to organizations because they could yield knowledge that could be utilized to conduct yet another dreadful disaster. More officially, it is used for reconnaissance purposes to learn more about a targeted network or host. A host can be attacked to learn the sorts of software installed and/or applications used. Reconnaissance attacks are relatively typical techniques of learning about the types and numbers of computers connected to a network.

c. User to Root (U2R):

These attacks are exploitations in which the hacker gains illegal access into the system using a regular user account and then tries to exploit security vulnerabilities to access administrative accounts with super-user privileges.

d. Remote to User (R2U):

A remote to user (sometimes known as R2L) is an attack launched in which the hacker wants to gain access to the user's device to send packets over its network, which s/he does not have access to expose the machines vulnerabilities and exploit privileges which a local user would have on the computer.

2. Cryptographic Attacks:

A cryptographic attack is a technique for circumventing a system's security by identifying a flaw in a cipher, security algorithm, cryptographic protocol, key

management scheme, or operating system. Another name for this method is "cryptanalysis." There are several types of attacks that might be classified as cryptanalysis [44]. These attacks include rubber cryptanalysis, crypto locker, known plaintext, known cipher-text, chosen cipher-text, chosen a key, and adaptive chosen plaintext assaults.

3. Cyber Threats:

Malicious attacks are also referred to as cyber threats. These threats aim to compromise the integrity of a company's or an individual's system by identifying security flaws in a cyber-physical system. Cyber danger seeks to harm or impair system performance.

There are many different forms of cyber threats that are currently available, and they can come from many primary sources, including people, physical attacks, equipment failure, line fault (failure node power lines), electromagnetic leakage, and electromagnetic interference (Zhang et al., 2013)[45].

4. Malicious software:

Malicious software (Malware) is used to hinder access restrictions, compromise the operation of cyber-physical systems, and steal data. Malicious software's primary goal is to harm the host computer [46]. A wide range of malicious codes is referred to as malicious software, which is a general word. Adware, bots, ransomware, bugs, rootkits, spyware, hackers, wabbits, dialers, blue sniffing, phishing, bluejacking, mouse trapping, pharming, and browser hijackers are the most prevalent types of malwares.

The Ukraine power grid cyber-attack is one of the infamous attacks made on SG systems used as a case study. The incident was the first of its kind, causing a cyber-induced power outage that affected an electric power grid. It occurred on December 23rd, 2015, and resulted in a "temporary breakdown of the power supply" in three regions, resulting in power outages lasting up to six hours and affecting 225,000 people across Ukraine [12].

The post-power loss analysis discovered that firmware on serial-to-Ethernet converters at substations was corrupted, uninterruptible power supplies (UPS) for the server room and the telephony system were remotely turned off, and multiple computers' hard drives were corrupted [47]. The Ukraine power outage was not caused by a single vulnerability [48]. Rather, a few minor network design and control flaws enabled the hostile actors to

eventually switch off the power. According to K. Zetter, studies and public accounts by the US Department of Homeland Security's Security Industrial Control Systems Cyber Response Team [49], personnel at the three operations centres were unable to retake remote control of the incident's more than 50 substations. Following a 6-hour outage and a loss of over 130 MW of load, management restored power by dispatching specialists to the substations and manually operating the power system.

Figure 2.3.2: Provinces Affected by the Ukraine Cyber-Induced Power Outage.

Also, a cyber-attack on a Saudi Arabian oil and gas corporation in 2012, the Shamoon malware-infected 30,000 of the company's window-based PCs, and it took three weeks for them to recover [50]. In 2017, a Saudi Arabian petrochemical factory was attacked, with the perpetrator destroying data, shutting down the plant, and causing physical damage [51]. The ransomware attack on Colonial Pipeline in the United States in 2021, in which attackers broke into the firm's networks and shut down the whole pipeline, disrupting fuel deliveries and costing the company \$5 million in ransom [52]. JBS Foods, the world's largest meat producer, also became a ransomware victim in June 2021, paying hackers \$11 million [53]. In addition, in 2010, the Stuxnet malware caused four zero-days in Iran's nuclear programme [54].

3.4 Machine Learning for Network Anomaly Detection

In recent years, machine learning (ML) methods are frequently prescribed for anomaly detection in these systems.

For intrusion detection for conventional cyber-physical systems (CPS), ML has established itself as a discriminator of harmful and abnormal events. Several machine-learning solutions have been investigated to identify anomalies, faults, and False Data Injection (FDI) in contemporary smart grids and power systems. There are three different categories of anomaly detection methods which are: supervised, semi-supervised, and unsupervised.

3.4.1 Supervised Machine Learning Methods

With supervised techniques, a classification algorithm is trained to separate various forms of anomalies from normal behaviour using an annotated training dataset. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) were used [55] to detect malicious management of distributed energy resources in a smart grid with a significant presence of photovoltaic (PV) generators. Despite the assumption of conditional independence that characterises the Naïve Bayes algorithm, Manikant [56] investigated its ability alongside Random Forests, in detecting highly masked cyber-attacks on smart grids. However, the complexity of the money determines the speed and effectiveness of this method for real-time implementation. Also, a Gaussian kernel support vector machine (SVM) was used by Esmalifalak et al. [57] to detect erroneous data injection in power flow measurements of the IEEE 118-bus test system. However, its work is confined to binary classification and cannot be extended to detect multiple types of attacks. Gob et al. also used Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) for identifying cyber-attacks in CPS [58].

3.4.2 Unsupervised Machine Learning Methods

Unsupervised anomaly detection uses an unlabeled dataset that searches for data points that deviate from the dataset's presumed normal points on the assumption that the vast majority of the data points are normal. However, this assumption always results in performance reduction when a small percentage of anomalous data is included in the unlabelled dataset.

A proposal for the use of Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBN) and Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBM) was made by Hadis et. al. [59], to discern a physical fault due to operational conditions from those due to cyber-attacks. However, the nature of the cost function prevented proper comparison with other documented methods, especially during the scenarios of single or multiple FDI attacks despite the high accuracy and low

false positive rate of this method. Another example is in the investigation of the use of isolation forests by Ahmed et al, to detect Covert Data Integrity Assaults (CDIAs) [60]. They also used a principal component analysis-based feature extraction technique and evaluated the model using standard IEEE 14-bus, 39-bus, 57-bus, and 118-bus systems. Their results showed an improvement in attack detection accuracy.

2.4.3 Semi-supervised Machine Learning Methods

With regards to semi-supervised anomaly detection algorithms, partially annotated data is used to model typical smart grid system behaviour before comparing the model's predictions to actual smart grid system behaviour. This category was developed to keep stable detection and combat the degradation in a performance recorded in unsupervised methods.

There are two significant limitations of current studies using a machine learning model to develop anomaly-based intrusion detection systems (IDS) for the smart power grid network. Firstly, there is no available research that shows or investigates that a hybrid and aggregation of data-driven Machine Learning models are more efficient and successful in detecting abnormalities on the smart grid network than a single machine learning model [14][15]. Secondly, the available studies documenting investigations of hybrid IDS for the internet of things network do not consider the smart grid network (cyber-physical systems) which uses multiple devices at multiple locations. Lastly, the researchers do not use datasets from the smart power grid network to test their studies, which makes their IDS unsuitable to be used in the smart power grid network [14].

These limitations motivated this project which uses a power system cyber-attack dataset from the Mississippi State University and Oak Ridge National Laboratory, to evaluate machine learning classification techniques for a hybrid Intrusion detection system for the smart power grid network.

4 Methodology

This section describes the approach to evaluating machine learning classification techniques for a hybrid Intrusion detection system. Different Machine learning models were developed, these models were supervised learning models using the classification scheme method over a binary class (Attack and normal operation) and three-class (Attack, Natural Disturbance, and No Event). The supervised classification learning algorithm was applied because the target variables are in classes.

4.1 Model development

Eleven sets of machine learning models were developed totally for the different target types, binary class (Attack and normal operation) and three-class (Attack, Natural Disturbance, and No Event). In the binary classification, 7 algorithms were developed, namely, decision tree, Logistic regression, support vector machine, Random Forest, Gradient Boost, Artificial neural network, and Voting classifier on three different binary datasets.

The different machine learning principles were considered to optimize the models' predictions. The overfitting and underfitting were considered and the variant among the data was also considered. To get the best result for the binary classification, the data was scaled, and the hyperparameter and features of the data were also considered and scaled. In developing the models, while some of the models were sensitive to data scales others were not, therefore, those that are sensitive to the data variation were scaled. In the three – classes classifications, 4 algorithms were developed, namely random Forest, support vector machine, Catboost, and Decision tree.

4.2 Data

The dataset was made from one initial dataset consisting of fifteen sets with 37 power system event scenarios in each.

- Three-class – The 37 event scenarios were grouped into 3 classes: attack events (28 events), natural events (8 events) or “No events” (1 event).

- Binary – The 37 event scenarios were grouped as either an attack (28 events) or normal operations (9 events). The data was drawn from 15 data sets which included thousands of individual samples of measurements throughout the power system for each event type [61].

4.2.1 Power System Description

The power system framework configuration required to generate these scenarios is depicted in the image below. There are various components in the network diagram, the first of which are power generators G1 and G2. R1–R4 are Intelligent Electronic Devices (IEDs) that can turn breakers on and off. These breakers are designated as BR1 through BR4. There are two of them. Line One connects breaker one (BR1) to breaker two (BR2), while Line Two connects breaker three (BR3) to breaker four (BR4) [62].

Figure 3.2.1: Experiment Network Diagram [62]

Scenarios are classified as follows:

1. Short-circuit fault - a short in a power line that can happen in a number of places along the wire; the location is indicated by the percentage range.
2. Line maintenance - one or more relays on a given line are turned off to perform maintenance on that line.
3. Remote tripping command injection (Attack) - An attack in which a command is sent to a relay, causing a breaker to open. It can only be done after an attacker has breached the perimeter defences.
4. Relay setting modification (Attack) - Relays are configured with a distance protection scheme, and the attacker modifies the setting to deactivate the relay function, preventing the relay from tripping for a valid fault or command.
5. Data Injection (Attack) - In this case, a real fault was imitated by modifying the values of parameters such as current, voltage, sequence components, and so on. The attacker's goal with this attack is to blind the operator and cause a blackout [62].

4.2.2 Data Acquisition

For this project, the Power System Cyber-Attack Datasets from Mississippi State University and Oak Ridge National Laboratory were used [62].

4.2.3 Data description

Six datasets in total were used to train and test the machine learning models, three datasets with binary classes and three datasets with 3 classes. The tables below describe the shapes of the various datasets that were used.

Binary Dataset

Table 3.2.3: The description for the binary classification datasets

	Data 1	Data 2	Data 3
--	--------	--------	--------

Features	129	129	129
Observations	4966	5415	5340

Three Class Dataset

Table 3.2.3.1: The description for the multi-class (3) classification datasets

	Data 1	Data 2	Data 3
Features	129	129	129
Observations	5340	5415	5161

4.2.4 Data Splitting

During the building of models in this project, each dataset was split into two, 70% (Trainset) and 30% (Testset) for training and testing respectively using Sci-kit learn. Shuffling was allowed in the splitting process to ensure that the classes in the target variable (marker) of the split data are in the same proportion as represented in the original data. The training dataset was further split into five folds for cross-validation and hyperparameter tuning to optimize models when necessary.

4.3 Modelling

Models were built by fitting the algorithms on the training dataset and tested on the test dataset by making predictions. Models were built on the entire training dataset, however, for models that required optimization by hyperparameter tuning, the training dataset was further split into five folds for grid search cross-validation. After the best hyperparameters were obtained, it was then fitted to the entire training dataset. Since not all the algorithms require data scaling to perform well, data scaling was kept in pipelines for the algorithms that required data scaling during model fitting.

4.3.1 Hyperparameter Tuning and Optimization

A hyper-parameter is a parameter with its value set at the beginning of training a model to control the learning process. The act of choosing the right values for hyperparameters to optimize a model is termed 'hyperparameter tuning'. Best hyperparameters' values are obtained by fitting models with different values and evaluating the results. To automate this step while at the same time avoiding information leakage, grid search cross validation was employed from the Sci-kit learn library to tune the parameters of the models that needed hyperparameter tuning to optimize their performance. Ranges of hyperparameters values were tried and values that optimized the models were chosen.

4.4 Model Architecture

In this research, some of the notable machine learning techniques will be used. The choice of machine learning models to use in this research was governed by two main criteria:

- Their inherent theoretical strength,
- Their popularity in recent literature for the network anomaly detection

With these criteria in place, the following models were chosen:

- Logistics Regression
- Support Vector Machine (Classifier)
- Decision Tree
- Ensemble Method
- Random Forest
- Gradient Boosting
- Voting Classifier
- Categorical Boosting
- Artificial Neural Network [35]

4.4.1 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a supervised learning algorithm used mostly for modelling classification problems. The simplest form of this algorithm is binary classification. This

algorithm estimate the probability or the likelihood of a class of a datasets (1/0, Yes/No, attack, no attack) using the sigmoid or logistic function, a S- shaped curve which can take real valued and map it into a value between 1 and 0 . It takes in the predictors (attributes) for the input variables (categorical or/and numerical variables) $X = x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ and response Y, a categorical variable (1, 0) [63]. The input variables are combined linearly by assigning weights to them with a bias to predict an output (response). Below is an equation for the logistic regression

$$(E(y)) = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_nx_n \quad 3.1$$

Where $E(y)$ is the predicted output, b_0 is the bias or intercept term, and b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n are weights or regression coefficients associated with each predictor. Because, the above is a form of linear regression which will results to a continuous value. Also, the output required for our predictions is between 1 and 0. Thus a sigmoid function is applied. Below is the graphical representation and an equation for sigmoid or logistic function.

Figure 3.4.1 the sigmoid function [64]

$$f(E(y)) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-(E(y))}} \quad 3.2$$

From the above graph, the following can be deduced:

$f(E(y))$ tends towards 1 as $E(y) \rightarrow \infty$

$f(E(y))$ tends towards 0 as $E(y) \rightarrow -\infty$

4.4.2 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

The formal definition of a Support Vector Machine (SVM), a discriminative classifier, is a separating hyperplane. To look at it another way, the technique creates an ideal hyperplane that categorises fresh samples from labelled training data (supervised learning). The purpose of the support vector machine technique is to find a hyperplane in N-dimensional space (N is the number of features) that clearly classifies the data points. There are numerous hyperplanes that could be utilised to separate the two groups of data points. The goal is to find a plane with the biggest margin, or separation, between data points from both classes. Increasing the margin distance increases the confidence with which subsequent data points can be classified [35].

Figure 3.3 Maximum margin Hyperplanes and margins for SVM

$$w \cdot x + b \geq 1 \text{ for } y = +1 \text{ class} \quad 3.3$$

$$w \cdot x + b \leq -1 \text{ for } y = -1 \text{ class} \quad 3.4$$

Above two equations can be written as:

$$y(w \cdot x + b) + 1 \geq 0 \text{ for } y = +1 \text{ and } -1 \text{ class} \quad 3.5$$

Suppose we have two hyperplane H_1 and H_2 passing through the support vectors of +1 and -1 class respectively. So

$$w \cdot x + b = -1 : H_1 \quad 3.6$$

$$w \cdot x + b = 1 : H_2 \quad 3.7$$

And distance between H_1 hyperplane and origin is $\frac{-1-b}{|w|}$ and distance between H_2 hyperplane and origin is $(1-b)/|w|$. So, margin can be given as:

$$M = \frac{(1-b)}{|w|} - \frac{(-1-b)}{|w|} \quad 3.8$$

$$M = \frac{2}{|w|} \quad 3.9$$

Where M is nothing but twice of the margin. So margin can be calculated as $\frac{1}{|w|}$. As, optimal hyperplane maximize the margin then SVM objective is boiled down to fact of maximizing the term $\frac{1}{|w|}$. This means $\min |w|$

As l_2 optimization are often more stable than l_1 optimization, thus the above equation can be re-written as:

$$\min \frac{|w|^2}{2}, \text{ such that } y(w \cdot x + b) + 1 \geq 0 \quad 3.10$$

To use it for multi-class, you need to change a parameter in the SVM call decision function. The decision function was changed to "OVO". SVM then uses the "One-to-One" approach, which breaks down the multiclass problem into multiple binary classification problems. A binary classifier per each pair of classes.

4.4.3 Decision Tree

Figure 3.4.3 A typical Decision Tree [65]

4.4.4 Ensemble Method

Ensemble modeling methods are methods where multiple diverse models are developed to predict an outcome, either by using many different model algorithms or training data sets. The ensemble model then aggregates the prediction of each base model and results in one final prediction. Numerous models in the machine learning literature fall under this category, but only three ensemble models—random forests, catboost, and gradient-boosted decision trees are successful at detecting anomalies. The primary aim of an ensemble model is to combine multiple machine learning models to create more powerful models [35].

4.4.4.1 Random Forest

A random forest is a collection of separate decision trees that are independent of each other. For each tree to be independent, the algorithm will generate different random options for each tree. The random forest algorithm creates a "forest" trained via bagging or bootstrap aggregation. Bagging is an ensemble meta-algorithm that improves the accuracy of machine learning algorithms. Random forests are built on the premise that

any tree may provide accurate predictions but will probably overfit some of the data. During this process, a bootstrap sample of our data is picked repeatedly at random, resulting in a data set that is roughly the size of the original dataset, with some data points missing and others repeating [35].

The algorithm then makes predictions using the mean or average output from different trees. The accuracy of the result grows as the number of trees increases. By eliminating these restrictions, a random forest method improves precision while decreasing overfitting.

4.4.4.2 Gradient Boosting

For regression and classification problems, gradient boosting is an ensemble boosting machine learning technique that creates a prediction model in the form of a collection of weak prediction models, often decision trees. Similar to other boosting techniques, it constructs the model in stages, but it generalizes them by enabling the optimization of any differentiable loss function.

This algorithm selects a function (weak hypothesis) that points in the direction of the negative gradient iteratively to maximize a cost function across the function space. Being a greedy method, gradient boosting can quickly overfit a training dataset. It can profit from regularization techniques that punish different aspects of the algorithm and, in general, enhance algorithm performance by lowering overfitting [66].

The steps taken by the algorithm are summarized below:

$$\text{Fit a model to the data, } F_1(x) = y \quad 3.12$$

$$\text{Fit a model to the residuals, } h_1(x) = y - F_1(x) \quad 3.13$$

$$\text{Create a new model, } F_2(x) = F_1(x) + h_1(x) \quad 3.14$$

Our final model can account for the flaws from the first model and gradually lowers this error by integrating weak learners after weak learners.

4.4.4.3 Voting Classifier

A voting classifier is a machine learning and ensemble estimator trained on several base models or estimators and predicts the outcome (response) with the highest probability. In simple terms, the algorithm predicts the output class based on the highest majority

(voting) after aggregating the results of each classifier submitted into the voting classifier. Instead of building individual specialized models and determining each one's accuracy, the goal is to create a single model that learns from multiple models and predicts results based on their aggregate majority of votes for each output class [67].

The Voting classifier enables two kind of aggregation methods:

- Hard Voting: The voting classifier estimator's predicted output is computed based on the class with the highest number of votes or the class with the greatest likelihood of being predicted by all the component classifiers.
- Soft voting: The final prediction is computed based on the average probability assigned to that class.

4.4.4.4 Categorical Boosting (CatBoost)

Categorical Boosting is an open-source boosting library developed by Yandex. In addition to regression and classification, it can be used in ranking, recommendation systems, forecasting and even personal assistants.

CatBoost uses a variant for practical purposes. In this variant, one tree structure (sequence of splitting features) is shared by all the models. That is, it uses the same D_k , that determined the ordered target statistics, as the data for determining the structure or fitting the decision tree h^t , and uses the complete dataset D as the data for evaluating whether h^t . The decision tree that minimizes the expected loss is. It uses multiple permutations to compute a number of sets of residual values that it can use to find h , to obtain F^{t-1} , and maintain the guarantee that none of the values of is used to compute the values of the gradients. Thereby reducing variance in the estimates of the gradients (rate of change of the loss function) and avoiding prediction shift [68].

4.4.5 Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

An artificial neuron network (neural network) is a computational model that mimics the way nerve cells work in the human brain. The organization of the neurons in the human brain is loosely represented in ANNs. In contrast to the brain, which has billions of neurons and a corresponding increase in the magnitude of their overall interaction and behaviour, a large ANN may have hundreds or thousands of processor units. Usually,

neural networks are segmented into layers. Each layer consists of numerous 'nodes' that are connected and an 'activation function. The "input layer" communicates with one or more "hidden layers," where processing takes place using a system of weighted "connections", to display patterns to the network [35].

A Multi-Layer perceptron is the simplest form of a neural network. The data passes through the input nodes and exits on the output nodes. This type of neural network may or may not have the hidden layers.

4.5 Model Performance Metrics

For evaluation of the performance of the machine learning models, an effective but standard measure of the generalization ability of each model, which is the performance metric, is required. Performance Analysis aims at comparing the precision and performance of machine learning models. In this research work, the machine learning models are evaluated and compared using four measures: Recall, Precision, F1-score, and AUC. According to the combination of exact event classes and algorithm prediction classes, the sample of predictions can be categorized into four cases: true positive (TP), false positive (FP), true negative (TN), and false negative (FN).

The "TN" stands for True Negative which shows the number of negative examples classified accurately. Similarly, "TP" stands for True Positive which indicates the number of positive examples classified accurately. The term "FP" shows False Positive value, i.e., the number of actual negative examples classified as positive; and "FN" means a False Negative value which is the number of actual positive examples classified as negative.

Accuracy

Accuracy is the ratio of the correctly predicted samples to the total number of samples.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad 3.16$$

Because accuracy might be deceptive when applied to imbalanced datasets, alternative metrics will be considered when assessing performance of the classification models [69].

Recall and Precision

Recall indicates the ratio of positive instances that are correctly detected by the classifier. Precision is calculated by dividing the total number of positive predictions by the proportion of actual positives [70]. The Recall and Precision formulas can be defined as follows:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad 3.17$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad 3.18$$

Where TP, FP and FN are the amounts of true positives, false positives and false negatives respectively.

F1 score

The F1 score measures the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall; however, due to the imbalanced nature of the datasets. This work adopted the weighted average of the F1 score for comparison. The weighted F1 score accounts for label imbalance, which calculates each label's scores and averages the scores. This measure in Equation (3) is expressed as:

$$F_1 = 2 \times \frac{precision \times recall}{precision + recall} \quad 3.19$$

$$F_1 \text{ weighted} = \frac{1}{w} \sum_i^N w_i \cdot F_i \quad 3.20$$

Where w_i and F_i are the weight and F1 score assigned to each class i in our dataset. w represents the sum of all weights w_i .

AUC_ROC curve

A Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (ROC) is a graph showing the performance of a classification model at all classification thresholds. This curve plots two parameters: true positive rate (TPR) and false positive rate (FPR). The AUC stands for "Area under the ROC Curve", a measure of the entire two-dimensional area underneath the ROC curve.

Overall, models for anomaly prediction are reported as accurate if AUC and F1 values are close to 1. Additional significant factors for evaluating the methods include their capacity

for generalization, rapidity, affordability of their implementation and operation, ease of use, low-cost maintenance, robustness, and simulation accuracy [70].

5 Evaluation

The projected results from the modelling were compared with the readings from Power systems cyber-attack datasets. After the model training and testing for each of the subsets of anomaly detection datasets, the suggested methodology was tested in two experiments.

Experiment 1 categorizes two classes and aims to differentiate between an attack and normal working conditions.

In Experiment 2, we aim to go further by distinguishing the nature of the attack recorded in experiment 1. Three different operating conditions—disturbance in smart grids, cyber-attack, and Normal network behaviour were simulated in the second experiment.

5.1 Binary Classification Model

The network anomaly dataset was trained and tested with seven machine learning algorithms to classify events accurately as normal operations or malicious attacks. Each model's performance was evaluated using the F1-score (weighted average), Precision, Recall, and AUC. Accuracy does not give a strong overall classifier performance when classes are imbalanced. As a result, it will not be considered for evaluating performance. The effectiveness of the trained models is contrasted in the table below.

Table 4.1.1 Models Performance of Binary Classification Models (Dataset I)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
SVM	0.9545	0.9948	0.9742	0.9141
GradientBoost	0.9637	0.9845	0.8883	0.9271
Decision Tree	0.9595	0.9595	0.9595	0.9085
Logistic Regression	0.8067	0.9603	0.8768	0.5756
ANN	0.9572	0.9853	0.9711	0.9154
Random Forest	0.9637	0.9844	0.974	0.9271
Voting Classifier	0.9573	0.9853	0.9711	0.9154

Table 4.1.2 Models Performance of Binary Classification Models (Dataset II)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
SVM	0.9530	0.9738	0.9633	0.9297
GradientBoost	0.9646	0.9755	0.8930	0.9451
Decision Tree	0.9441	0.9458	0.9442	0.9064
Logistic Regression	0.7217	0.9318	0.8134	0.5387
ANN	0.9629	0.9755	0.9692	0.9431
Random Forest	0.9646	0.9755	0.9700	0.9451
Voting Classifier	0.9629	0.9755	0.9692	0.9431

Table 4.1.3 Models Performance of Binary Classification Models (Dataset III)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
SVM	0.9545	0.9948	0.9742	0.9032
GradientBoost	0.9253	0.9711	0.8281	0.9064
Decision Tree	0.9149	0.9337	0.9242	0.8793
Logistic Regression	0.6941	0.8833	0.7773	0.5490
ANN	0.9335	0.9692	0.9510	0.9149
Random Forest	0.9253	0.9711	0.9476	0.9064
Voting Classifier	0.9335	0.9692	0.9510	0.9149

To obtain a summarised measure of each model's performance, we employ a measure of central tendency (mean). This will enable an ideal performance measure across all datasets considered in this work. The average performance indicators for a train-test split are shown in the figures below.

From the above plots (Figure 4.1 a-d) and statistical metrics (Table 4.1.1 - 4.1.3), it can be observed that amongst all intelligent models used, SVM performed better in terms of F1-score and Recall, whereas Random Forests performed better in terms of AUC and Precision. With high precision but low recall (Random Forests), a classifier is incredibly accurate but misses many difficult instances to classify. This is not very useful. Hence, the nature of this problem prompted an emphasis on the F1 score. This is because it reveals a classifier's precision (the proportion of correctly classified cases) and robustness (the ability not to miss a significant number of instances).

The difference between SVM and Random Forests in terms of Recall suggests that SVM is a better model. The SVM model documented an average F1 score of 0.9651 across all datasets.

5.2 Three Class classification Model

Here, we trained four machine learning algorithms on a different variation of the network anomaly dataset. The datasets used here contain three events to be classified, as explained in the earlier section. Each model's performance was evaluated using the same evaluation metrics specified in 4.1.

Table 4.2.1 Models Performance of Multiclass Classification Models (Dataset I)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
SVM	0.9265	0.927	0.9256	0.9677
Random Forest	0.9318	0.9307	0.9292	0.986
Decision Tree	0.8948	0.8951	0.8949	0.9046
Catboost Classifier	0.9379	0.9376	0.9363	0.9779

Table 4.2.2 Models Performance of Multiclass Classification Models (Dataset II)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
SVM	0.9607	0.9605	0.9596	0.9891
Random Forest	0.9662	0.9663	0.9657	0.9905
Decision Tree	0.9255	0.9249	0.9251	0.8996
Catboost Classifier	0.9634	0.9637	0.9635	0.9816

Table 4.2.3 Models Performance of Multiclass Classification Models (Dataset III)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	AUC
SVM	0.9556	0.9555	0.9549	0.9883
Random Forest	0.9612	0.9613	0.9609	0.9919
Decision Tree	0.9315	0.9316	0.9315	0.9260
Catboost Classifier	0.9526	0.9529	0.9525	0.9837

To obtain a summarised measure of each model's performance, we employ a measure of central tendency (mean). This will enable an ideal performance measure across all datasets considered in this work. The average performance indicators for a train-test split are shown in the figures below.

From the above plots (Figure 4.2 a-d) and statistical metrics (Table 4.2.1 - 4.2.3), it can be observed that amongst all intelligent models used, Catboost performed better with an average AUC of 0.9867 and a weighted F1 score of 0.9541. Notice that Random Forests (another ensemble) is the runner-up in this experiment.

Compared to other cutting-edge machine learning approaches, It is observed that given a set of machine learning models, hybrid/ensemble methods are quite capable and show significant improvement in the classification performance for multiclass cases. The Catboost ensemble technique is promising since it can precisely categorize specific attack types as opposed to an SVM, which is better for the binary identification of faults while keeping high accuracy.

6 Future Work

There have been three limitations of this project. Inability to test hybrid model viability using industry power grid architectures such as the IEEE 118-bus test system. Also, access to quality big data and data containing more classes of attack. Again, test your results in a real-time smart grid network infrastructure. Lastly, lack of computational resources to build deep learning models. The project has shown that combining multiple machine learning into an intrusion detection system makes detecting anomalies in smart grid power systems suitable. However, Network Intrusion detection systems need a real-world dataset. A real-world smart grid network dataset would help with a real, efficient comparison between the different machine learning models. Also, access to big quality

data would ensure the ability to train deeper ensembles and complex models for better performance.

Furthermore, the inability to test hybrid model viability using industry power grid architectures such as the IEEE 118-bus test system will not help validate your results. A dataset benchmark enables training, validating, and evaluating studies using machine learning algorithms. Testing your results in a real-time smart grid network infrastructure help validate the result. In this project, two classes and three class classifications were used. Access to data containing more classes of attack would ensure the development of a robust model to distinguish more than 3 classes of attacks accurately. Because deep learning methods are based on learning high-level abstract representations, they will be able to detect zero-day attacks [71].

In the future, more efforts must be made to detect unknown and zero-day attacks in smart grid networks and develop IDSs that can automatically update the list of the considered attacks when new ones appear [71]. Also, consider more diverse attack scenarios and incorporate more machine-learning algorithms to improve the detection accuracy for anomalies on a smart grid network [60].

7 Conclusion

A smart grid is supposed to create a complex, intelligent electric grid network with increased efficiency, high resiliency, and reliability. Due to the highly complex architecture of the smart grid network, it is being exploited by security attacks. Therefore, to achieve a high level of security against attacks on the smart grid network, this dissertation demonstrates that combining multiple machine learning algorithms in an intrusion detection system will help detect smart power grid attacks.

In this project, four multiclass and seven binary class algorithms were trained and tested with Industrial Control System (ICS) power system cyber-attack dataset. The eleven machine learning algorithms were trained with 70% of three binary class datasets and multiclass (3 classes) datasets. Models built from machine learning algorithms that combine several models were compared with single models from machine learning algorithms, particularly SVM. Because the data was imbalanced, weighted AUC, F1 Score,

Precision Score, and Recall Score metrics were used in model comparison to account for the imbalance.

Out of the seven models built on binary datasets, models from ensemble algorithms like Random Forest, Catboost, and Voting classifier, which combine several models, outperformed single models from the decision tree algorithm, Logistic regression algorithm, and Support vector Machine algorithm. Similarly, in the multiclass (3 class) case, models from ensembles (Random Forest, Catboost) outperformed single models from the decision tree algorithm and Support Vector Machine algorithm.

Studies have proven that the Support Vector Machine gives very high accuracy and outperforms other machine learning models regarding network anomaly detection. With this project, based on the overall model average F1 Score, Catboost and Random Forest, which are ensembles, follow SVM in terms of performance in the binary dataset case, but in the 3-class dataset case, SVM was outperformed by Catboost and Random Forest.

With a smart power grid dataset, we have proven that different machine learning models have different capabilities in predicting attacks based on data complexity. Hence integrating multiple machine learning models into a single Intrusion Detection System will help to detect attacks on a complex and sophisticated communication network such as Smart Grid.

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